

**CULTURAL STUDIES AND INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES THAT
SERVE TO ENRICH IT AND THEIR ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE
PROFESSIONAL THINKING OF PEDAGOGUES**

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The civilization that we are living in is a dynamic, always changing and evolving society. New information and qualifications are constantly being added to the educational system of the modern world. New areas of interaction and specialties that comprise with new disciplines are developing. Reforms are being made to higher education worldwide, which led to the hunt for new educational technology and formats. Higher education is developed in accordance with a number of guiding concepts in order to align with global norms and criteria. Hence, foremost it is the introduction of innovative achievements in science and in the system of education. It is well recognized that the creation of a generation of people who think and operate in new ways depends on the innovative ways in which society develops. Therefore, the main attention is on the development of personality in cultural and communicative ways. In light of this, the article's primary goal is to examine the key components of cutting-edge pedagogical technologies in the educational system.

The significant difficulty of modernizing educational establishments, which are frequently strict and outmoded, exists throughout the world. The world is transforming quickly. Too many students lack motivation and perform much below their capabilities. Aspirational goals are being set for educational systems around the world at the same time. For all of these reasons, educational institutions and systems need to be prepared to step outside their comfort zones and abandon the tried-and-true. Creativity is crucial.

Significant changes in curriculum policy also support educational innovation. In many nations, curriculum policy measures encourage the development of competences, particularly those frequently referred to as "21st century skills." Competencies like teamwork, perseverance, creativity, and invention are more inherent to various teaching and learning methods through pedagogy than they are taught. Pedagogies must purposefully nurture 21st century competencies if they are to be systematically cultivated as opposed to being allowed to happen by accident.

Therefore, innovation is essential and must be used by the pedagogies all over the world. The cultivation of pedagogical knowledge is crucial since it is the basis of teacher professionalism. However, given the lack of accepted definitions and the sheer quantity and fluidity of the relationships involved, patterns of educational practice are incredibly difficult to comprehend at a system level (much alone internationally). However, because of how crucial it is, it cannot be kept in a "black box" hidden behind the classroom's doors.

According to the analytical report of UNESCO "The Post-2015 Sustainable Development Program" noted that in the new information era, the most important place took higher education. Therefore, in many spheres of public activity the direction of progress and innovation includes high dynamism, rapid change in knowledge, information and technology. In such conditions, the social importance of the state is increasing in ensuring access to quality education, a high level of knowledge, the possibility of acquiring relevant skills and competencies through the provision of academic mobility and freedom to higher educational institutions.

The purpose of education in the development of an inventive society is to enable students to understand and put into practice new scientific concepts, theories, tools, and methodologies. In order to impart to them the information and skills they have acquired over the years.

The environment in which we are living becoming complicated and conflicting. One of the most significant objectives of a higher school is the personal and professional development of students because it takes a sufficiently high level of intellectual and creative capacity as well as high professionalism to build a reasonable strategy for one's own life. In order to execute students' personal and professional growth, pedagogical practice necessitates the development of a toolbox that is both comparatively straightforward and simultaneously the most general. The structure of this evolution and its dynamics in cutting-edge learning technologies, mimicking the educational environment itself, should be made clear through this tool. The key elements of education - content, forms, methodologies, teaching technologies, methodological support (including textbooks), and teacher roles - should be examined in this perspective.

New terms like "pedagogical technologies," "pedagogical," and "teaching technologies" have evolved from the original term. Educational technologies serve the purpose of predicting educational development, its specific design and planning, predicting results, and determining the corresponding educational goals and standards. They also reflect the general strategy for the development of education, a unified educational space. The ideas of education and the educational system are examples of educational technologies. This is currently a humanistic conception of education, a system of education, and others.

Pedagogical technologies, which introduce models of both the latter and identical models of controlling this process, embody the tactics of its application in the educational process if educational technologies reflect the strategy of education. For instance, a model of developmental learning that is personality-oriented, modular, problem-based. Therefore, pedagogical technology integrates the content, forms, and means of each of them to reflect the model of the instructional and managerial processes of an educational institution.

The idea of teaching technology is similar to, but not the same as, the idea of pedagogical technology. It displays the method of understanding a certain educational component (concept) inside the relevant academic course, topic, or problem, requires a unique organization of educational material as well as suitable formats and teaching strategies. However, the following choices are also viable. The content and methods of instruction are arranged so that they are matched to the instructional formats or instructional strategies. As an example, subject learning, game technology, problem learning technology (at the method level), information technology, technology for using support schemes, abstracts, traditional lecture training, training using audiovisual technical means or books, consulting, individual, distance learning, computer training, etc.

The quality of the teacher's pedagogy indicates their level of expertise. According to his teaching and rearing practices, the subjects of his training and education will develop to varying degrees. Therefore, it is clear that the ideas of "educational technology," "pedagogical technology," and "educational technology" are all related to the concept of "pedagogical technology."

Some fundamental methodological standards and criteria for manufacturability must be addressed by pedagogical technology:

- conceptuality (reliance on a concept that provides philosophical, psychological, didactic, and socio-pedagogical justifications for educational goals);
- consistency (pedagogical development must have all features of the system);
- consistency of the process, the interconnection of all its parts, integrity;
- manageability (the ability to set goals, design the learning process, use step-by-step diagnostics, and use a variety of means and methods to correct the result).

A synthesis of pedagogical science's and practice's accomplishments, modern pedagogical technology combines traditional aspects of past knowledge with those brought about by social and technological advancement, humanization, democratization of society, and technological revolution. Social changes and pedagogical thinking, social, pedagogical, and psychological sciences, contemporary advanced teaching experience, historical domestic and international experience (acquisition of earlier generations), and folk pedagogy are the sources and constituents of new educational technologies.

There are a variety of instructional devices available in contemporary pedagogical thought and practice. Each educational tool has its own procedural traits (motivational, managerial, student category), as well as software and methodological support (curriculum and programs, teaching aids, didactic materials, visual and technological teaching aids, diagnostic interpretations). Interactive educational technology has recently played a significant role in higher education. The core idea behind interactive technologies is that learning happens through student participation. Both the teacher and the pupils are learning subjects.

Interactive learning has the unique benefit of teaching students how to collaborate effectively using cooperation skills. This issue can be resolved with the appropriate, planned, and systematic usage of interactive technologies. Interactive teaching techniques are a component of student-centered learning because they help people become more socially aware, aware of their place in a team, and aware of their potential.

Innovative learning is an ongoing effort to reevaluate values, retaining those that are indisputable essential while discarding those that are already out of date. Innovations in educational activities include the proactive process of developing and disseminating new methods and means of solving didactic problems of training specialists in a harmonious combination of traditional methods and the findings of creative research, the use of unconventional, forward-thinking technologies, original didactic ideas, and forms of ensuring the educational process.

Since the necessity for reorganizing education and the creation of a suitable educational and material base in our nation is already apparent, solving urgent pedagogical problems effectively, consistently, and quickly is important in the modern world. This can be aided by new pedagogical and informational technology. One cannot be separated from the other because only through the wide adoption of new pedagogical technologies will the paradigm of education be changed, and only through new information technologies will the potential of new pedagogical technologies be most fully realized. The ability to fully disclose the didactic and pedagogical purposes of the approaches, as well as to realize the potential possibilities they contain, is made feasible by modern information technologies.

Innovative education is a complicated process that needs competent, helpful supervision. The implementation of cutting-edge pedagogical technologies has had a tremendous impact on

how education is conducted, making it easier to address issues with student-centered learning, differentiation, humanization, and the construction of unique educational perspectives.

Both conventional and cutting-edge teaching techniques, which are equally successful in the modern learning process, should be used; in some circumstances, they are simply indispensable. They must always interact with one another and support one another. Both of these ideas must be present at the same level.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the integration of innovative technologies into the pedagogical process of the educational system of higher educational institutions leads to an improvement in the quality indicators of students' academic achievements as well as an increase in the pedagogical skills and professional competence of future teachers - participants in innovative processes. The development of universities is tracked in tandem with the modernization of the entire regional educational system, and it is supported scientifically and methodologically. This is done by looking for, developing, and implementing cutting-edge pedagogical technologies. The development of a modern style of thinking with its distinguishing traits - creativity, consistency, flexibility, dynamism, perspective, objectivity, conceptuality. Hence, it is observed at the level of a specialist's personality.

As a result, when cutting-edge pedagogical technology enters the educational process, they will gradually and very naturally replace established working practices. Taking into account the unique characteristics of higher education around the globe and the global cultural condition, higher education institutions will be able to design an ideal method for structuring the educational process in this situation culture.

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